

Prognosis of COVID-19 Depends on Pathophysiology and Preexisting Health Condition: A Review

Md Al Hasibuzzaman^{1*}, Binbin Zhu², Rinki Kumari³, Mohammad Arman Hossain⁴, Md. Mahfujul Haque Haidary⁵, Muhammad Sharjeel Khalid⁶, Dattatreya Mukherjee⁷, Md. Munnaf Hossen⁸

¹Ningbo University, School of Medicine, Ningbo City, Zhejiang Province, PR China, 315211.

²The Affiliated Hospital of Medical School of Ningbo University, Ningbo City, Zhejiang Province, PR China 315211

³Department of Microbiology, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Sitapur Rd, Uttar Pradesh, India-261303

⁴First Affiliated Hospital of Chongqing Medical University, Chongqing, China.

⁵Wuxi School of Medicine, Jiangnan University, 1800 Lihu Ave, Wuxi, China

⁶Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad (38000), Pakistan

⁷International School, Jinan University, P.R China.

⁸Department of Immunology, Health Science Center, Shenzhen University, Shenzhen, China.

Accepted June 18, 2021
Published June 24, 2021

*Corresponding Author:
Md Al Hasibuzzaman,
hasibuzzaman.hsb@gmail.com

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5028954>

Pages: 130-138

Funding: No Funding

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA): Al Hasibuzzaman, M., Zhu, B. Kumari, R., Arman Hossain, N., & Haque Haidary, M. (2021). Prognosis Of COVID-19 Depends on Pathophysiology and Preexisting Health Condition: A Review. *North American Academic Research*, 4(6), 130-138. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5028954>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has changed the situation of the world. In December 2019, an unknown variant of pneumonia disease occurred in Wuhan, China. On Jan 7, 2020, a novel coronavirus, named severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2), was announced in the throat swab sample of one patient in Wuhan. COVID-19 has spread quickly around the world, affecting millions of people. The World Health Organization (WHO) announced the epidemic disease caused by SARS-CoV-2 as coronavirus.

This article review summarizes the epidemiological characteristics, pathophysiological changes, clinical diagnosis, treatment procedure, and prognosis of COVID-19. A comprehensive understanding of COVID-19 through research will help control the disease and increase awareness in public and medical domains.

Keywords: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; 2019-nCoV; Coronaviruses; SARS; MERS, COVID-19 PATHOPHYSIOLOGY, CORONAVIRUSES PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

1. Introduction

Coronavirus has been around for more than 50 years, affecting both animals and human beings. The molecular mechanisms of replication and the pathogenesis of several coronaviruses have been actively studied since the 1970s. Some of the animal viruses, such as porcine transmissible gastroenteritis virus (TGEV), bovine coronavirus (BCoV), and avian infectious bronchitis viruses (IBV), are of veterinary importance¹.

Coronavirus has lots of common syndromes, which resemble a common cold and fever. Studies have shown that the Coronavirus outbreak in 2003 was responsible for the severe acute

respiratory syndrome (SARS) epidemic. Common SARS symptoms include a fever, a cough, fatigue, shortness of breath or breathing difficulties, and loss of smell. Two human respiratory coronaviruses have been found. However, newly found SARS-CoV-2 (Feb 11, 2020), the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses, renamed the virus severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2).

The SARS-CoV-2 has resulted in clinically confirmed cases of 117 million recently. WHO declared that COVID-19 was listed as the sixth Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC), implicating that it may be dangerous to various countries and entailed an international response alerting the medical community about the two types of carriers: those with COVID-19 symptoms and those that were asymptomatic. Asymptomatic patients may not seek medical care, and even if they did, they might not get diagnosed. Patients falling in this category are at higher risk to the community since they become active carriers and potential sources for spreading the virus. Spike protein has been considered the ultimate target for COVID-19 immunotherapies, and this is based on SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV preceding evidence. Recent studies have found that SARS-CoV S protein-induced polyclonal antibody responses and counteracted SARS-CoV-2 S mediated entry into host cells, thus favoring the use of this ideal molecular target for vaccination and immunotherapies. Because the symptoms like fever are not recognized quickly, the false-positive results came out. A patient needs the maximum average time from exposure to symptom onset to be five days, and 97.5% of people who develop symptoms do so within 11.5 days. The most common symptoms are fever, dry cough, and shortness of breath. Radiographic and laboratory abnormalities, such as lymphopenia and elevated lactate dehydrogenase, are common but nonspecific².

In-hospital data, 5% of patients who have COVID-19 and 20% of the patients admitted with severe symptoms; necessitating Intensive critical care, more than 80% of the people who need critical care and supplemental oxygen². The way to treat the COVID-19 patients should be acute hypoxic respiratory failure. Emerging data indicate that dexamethasone therapy reduces 28-day mortality in patients requiring supplemental oxygen compared with usual care (21.6%vs 24.6%; age-adjusted rate ratio, 0.83 [95%CI, 0.74-0.92]) and that Remdesivir improves time to recovery (hospital discharge or no supplemental oxygen requirement) from 15 to 11 days. (Review Wiersinga, 2020). SARS-CoV-2 is believed to cross-species to initiate primary human infections; it is now spread primarily by human-to-human transmission. Although the case fatality rate of COVID-19 (estimated at 2%–3%) is lower than those of SARS (approximately 10%) and MERS (approximately 40%), the pandemic associated with COVID-19 has been far more severe³.

2. Pathophysiological changes

Coronavirus is a large, heavy droplet, single-based RNA virus that is found in humans and mammals. It is also noticed in dogs, cats, chickens, pigs, birds, etc. Coronavirus causes acute respiratory syndrome. The most common coronaviruses in clinical practice are 229E, OC43, NL63, and HKU1, which typically cause common cold symptoms in immunocompetent individuals. SARS-CoV-2 is the third coronavirus that has caused severe disease in humans to spread globally in the past two decades⁴. Coronavirus can infect a new host through genetic

recombination. Bates is the natural preserver of SARS-CoV-2, but it transmits to humans by the intermediate host such as Pangolin.

Table 1⁵ (It is showing the breathing problems, analytical data of the different type of COVID19 patients)

Knowledge	Total N = 1,000	Educational groups			P-value
		≤High school n = 205	Bachelor degree n = 634	Master/Ph.D. or above n = 161	
Incubation period : 2–14 days	957	183 (89.27%)	616 (97.16%)	158 (98.14%)	0.001
Symptoms					
Difficulty in breathing	909	172 (83.9%)	582 (91.8%)	155 (96.27%)	0.001
High temperature/Fever	898	170 (82.93%)	571 (90.06%)	157 (97.52%)	0.001
Cough	839	158 (77.07%)	533 (84.07%)	148 (91.93%)	0.001
Sore throat	542	101 (49.27%)	325 (51.26%)	116 (72.05%)	0.001
Tiredness	531	83 (40.49%)	351 (55.36%)	97 (60.25%)	0.001
Complications					
Pneumonia	794	136 (66.34%)	515 (81.23%)	143 (88.82%)	0.001
Kidney failure	228	32 (15.61%)	136 (21.45%)	60 (37.27%)	0.001
Sepsis and septic shock	76	6 (2.93%)	49 (7.73%)	21 (13.04%)	0.001
Population at high risk					
Elderly age ≥ 65 years	745	141 (68.78%)	471 (74.29%)	133 (82.61%)	0.010
People with comorbid conditions	686	111 (54.15%)	444 (70.03%)	131 (81.37%)	0.001
Health care workers	560	94 (45.85%)	364 (57.41%)	102 (63.35%)	0.002
Personal protection measures					
Social distancing	923	178 (86.83%)	595 (93.85%)	150 (93.17%)	0.004
Avoid travel to infected area or country	869	165 (80.49%)	564 (88.96%)	140 (86.96%)	0.008
Avoid things made in china	162	51 (24.88%)	102 (16.09%)	9 (5.59%)	0.001
Treatment available for COVID 19					
No treatment till date	764	138 (67.32%)	487 (76.81%)	139 (86.34%)	0.001
Supportive treatment	471	61 (30.24%)	317 (50%)	92 (55.14%)	0.001

P < 0.05 is considered statistically significant (Chi square test), n, Number of participants; HCWs, health care workers (including doctors, nurses, and pharmacist), other residents: including employed, unemployed, and students.

Early in infection, SARS-CoV-2's target cells are nasal and bronchial epithelial cells and pneumocystis, going through the viral structural spike protein binds SARS-CoV-2 angiotensin-converting enzyme. Past similar to respiratory viral diseases, such as rhinovirus disease, profoundly neutropenia occurs in individuals with COVID-19, but SARS-CoV-2 infects and kills T lymphocyte cells. To elucidate why SARS-S and SARS-2-S mediated entry into the same cell lines, we next determined whether SARS-2-S harbors amino acid residues required for interaction with the SARS-S entry receptor ACE2. Sequence analysis revealed that SARS-CoV-2 clusters with SARS-CoV-related viruses from bats (SARSr-CoV), of which some but not all can use ACE2 for host cell entry. To gain more insight into the expression patterns of genes associated with ACE2, we performed Spearman's correlation analysis with Benjamini–Hochberg-adjusted P values to identify genes associated with ACE2 across all cells within the lung epithelial cell datasets. While the correlation coefficients are relatively low (<0.12), likely due to low expression of ACE2, technical noise, and dropout effects, the expression pattern of the top 50 ACE2-correlated genes across the respiratory tree is consistent with that of ACE2, with a skewed expression toward upper airway cells⁶. Autopsy studies have shown how to diffuse thickening of the alveolar cell wall with mononuclear cells and macrophages infiltrating airspaces in addition to endothelialitis.

Dysregulation by the host response to infection may further contribute to causing multi-organ failure⁷. Collectively, an endothelial barrier of the irruption, dysfunctional alveolar-capillary of oxygen transmission, and impaired oxygen time of diffusion capacity are characteristic features of COVID-19. A report from Wuhan, China, indicated that 71% of 183 individuals who died of COVID-19 met the criteria for diffuse intravascular coagulation. Effective antiviral immunity is fostered through cooperative interactions between the host's specific innate and adaptive immune responses during viral infections. Antigen-presenting cells recognize and process viral antigens into smaller peptides later attached to major histocompatibility complex (MHC) class I/II molecules⁸.

3. Epidemiological characteristics

The virus data suggest that this virus is transmitted via airborne droplets during talking, coughing, or sneezing when people come face to face within six feet. Symptomatic patients, if they encounter community members for at least 15 minutes, if they cough or sneeze, are at a higher risk of transmitting this virus. Less chances of transmission in asymptomatic person's contacts, whether in brief exposures. Contact surface spread (touching surface with virus nit) is method transmission. The Bayesian analysis revealed that the prevalence of symptoms significantly varied according to age. The clinical presentation of young COVID-19 patients more frequently included ear, nose, and throat symptoms, that is, loss of smell, nasal obstruction, rhinorrhea, facial pain, headache, and throat pain, compared with elderly individuals, who more frequently presented fever, fatigue, loss of appetite and diarrhea ($P < 0.010$)⁹.

The figure1:¹⁰, (Relationship how COVID-19 spread quickly and how to spread It quickly)

The pattern to spread Covid-19 is not self-isolation. Not maintaining social distancing, engaging in outdoor activities, or traveling without wearing a mask can be highly dangerous.

4. Clinical diagnosis

The complete clinical manifestation is not found yet, as the past data and reports suggest that symptoms range from mild to severe; some cases might result in death. The most common and clinical data report found fever, cough, fatigue, pneumonia, and myalgia. Other less common symptoms are a headache, diarrhea, phlegm-producing cough, runny nose, and hemoptysis. Patients with mild symptoms were reported that they recovered in one week. However, severe symptoms were found progressive respiratory failure because of alveolar damage, which ultimately causes death. Such cases are reported in elderly patients and middle age who primarily experience diseases like diabetes, coronary heart failure, hyperbaton, Parkinson's disease, heart disease, tumor surgery, etc. Patients with the suspected infection must follow procedures that have been suggested for diagnosis: real-time fluorescence (RT-PCR) to detect the positive Nucleic acid test of SARS-CoV-2 in sputum, throat swabs, and secretions of the lower respiratory tract samples.

5. Prevention and control protocol

There are three levels of prevention and control strategies methods that are known. National level, case-related population, and general population-level prevention. At the national level, the National Health Commission of the People's Republic of China issued the "No.1 announcement" on Jan 20, 2020, which officially included COVID-19 into the management of Class B legal infectious diseases and allowed for an infectious disease preventive and control measures to be implemented. Under this policy, medical institutes can adopt isolation treatment and observation protocols to prevent and control the spread of COVID-19. On Jan 22, 2020, the National Health Commission published national guidelines for preventing and controlling COVID-19 for medical institutes¹¹. The World Health Organization declared on Mar 11, 2020, that COVID-19 is a pandemic. The World Health Organization has lots of protocols and guidelines. It has requested all the governments to shut down public transportation and maintain social distance. The World Health Organization has given Country-level coordination, planning, monitoring guidelines, Serology, early investigation protocols, risk communication, community engagement, essential resource planning, and infection prevention and control guidelines. The WHO also issued detailed guidelines on the use of face masks in the community, during care at home, and in the health care settings of the COVID-19 situation. In this document, health care workers are recommended to use Particulate respirators such as those certified N95 or FFP2 when performing aerosol-generating procedures. Also, need to use medical masks while providing any care to suspected or confirmed cases. According to this guideline, individuals with respiratory symptoms are advised to use medical masks in health care and home care and should adequately follow the infection prevention guidelines.

Conclusion

My review showed the present and future aspects of the COVID-19 situation. During this time, much research was published about the outbreak of clinical manifestation, diagnosis, causes, epidemiology, prevention, and control of the coronavirus. Most of the studies are trying to show the clinical data and diagnosis. This study focused on the overall review of the outbreak of the COVID-19 condition. Worldwide medical professionals and scientists work at the national level to prevent this public health pandemic both short term and long term. We recommended that the scholarly community should find ways to prevent long-term and short-term public health emergencies.

Acknowledgment

I sincerely thank Vijay Patankar from the University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China, for reviewing the article and being my mentor. I also want to mention Sara Zabeen, University Lecturer from Charles Darwin University; She taught me about Research methodology. I want to thank also my Professor Binbin Zhu from Ningbo University, School of Medicine. I want to especially thank Zinia Pervin from the Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of New Mexico.

References

1. Weiss SR, Navas-martin S. Coronavirus Pathogenesis and the Emerging Pathogen Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus. *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev.* 2005 Dec;69(4):635-64..
2. W Joost Wiersinga, Andrew Rhodes. Pathophysiology, Transmission, Diagnosis, and Treatment of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) A Review. *JAMA.* 2020 Aug 25;324(8):782-793.
3. Shi Y, Wang G, Cai X peng. An overview of COVID-19. *J Zhejiang Univ Sci B.* 2020 May;21(5):343-360.
4. Hoffmann M, Kleine-weber H, Schroeder S. SARS-CoV-2 Cell Entry Depends on ACE2 and TMPRSS2 and Is Blocked by a Clinically Proven Article SARS-CoV-2 Cell Entry Depends on ACE2 and TMPRSS2 and Is Blocked by a Clinically Proven Protease Inhibitor. *Cell.* 2020 Apr 16;181(2):271-280.
5. Tripathi R, Alqahtani SS, Albarraq AA, Meraya AM. Awareness and Preparedness of COVID-19 Outbreak Among Healthcare Workers and Other Residents of South-West Saudi Arabia: A Cross-Sectional Survey. *Front Public Health.* 2020 Aug 18;8:482.
6. Sungnak W, Huang N, Bécavin C, Berg M, Queen R, Litvinukova M. SARS-CoV-2 entry factors are highly expressed in nasal epithelial cells together with innate immune genes. *Nat Med.* 2020 May;26(5):681-687
7. Pervin Z, Hassan MM. Synergistic therapeutic actions of antimicrobial peptides to treat multidrug-resistant bacterial infection. *Reviews in Medical Microbiology.* 2021 March; 32 (2), 83-89.
8. Olwenyi OA, Dyavar SR, Acharya A, Podany AT, Fletcher C V. Immuno-epidemiology and pathophysiology of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *J Mol Med (Berl).* 2020 Oct;98(10):1369-138.
9. Lechien JR, Chiesa-estomba CM, Place S, Laethem Y Van. Clinical and epidemiological characteristics of 1420 European patients with mild-to-moderate coronavirus disease 2019. *J Intern Med.* 2020 Sep;288(3):335-344.
10. Son H, Lee H, Lee M, Eun Y, Park K, Kim S. Epidemiological characteristics of and containment measures for COVID-19 in Busan, Korea. *Epidemiol Health.* 2020 June ;42:e2020035.
11. Adhikari SP, Meng S, Wu Y, Mao Y, Ye R, Wang Q. Epidemiology, causes, clinical manifestation and diagnosis, prevention and control of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) the early outbreak period : a scoping review. *Infect Dis Poverty.* 2020 Mar 17;9(1):29.

Authors name and details:

1. Md Al Hasibuzzaman

Author Information: Md Al Hasibuzzaman is a medical graduate, research assistant in The Affiliated Hospital of Medical School of Ningbo University. He has a research interest in Neurology, Cardiology, Oncology, clinical trials, Public health, and Nephrology. He has been working with Clinical research and has a vision for a Clinical research carrier in academia and have a PhD. Phone :+8801723202217

2. Binbin Zhu

Author Information: I am an anesthesiologist and I spent a lot of time taking care of the patient, during the COVID-19 I monitored the vital signs on patient who was suspected to be infected. And I also working with other people to find the psychological burden of the family of doctors.

3. Rinki Kumari

Author Information: An enthusiastic and young medical educator and researcher seeking a teaching position in an organization that offers potential for career growth as well as opportunities to utilize my experience. Excellent interpersonal skills, capable of adjusting to challenging and changing environments. To attain challenging task force responsibility in a well-established cellular and molecular genetics laboratory in health organization (medical) such as IMS, that will provide me to explore the knowledge of syndromes and non-syndromes diseases with the aim how to diagnosed the patients at molecular level and current task as molecular biologist for Covid19 investigation

4. Mohammad Arman Hossain

Author Information: I am Dr. Mohammad Arman Hossain, Hailing from Bangladesh. I finished my MBBS from Dhaka, Bangladesh, and my Master's in Urology from Chongqing, China. Now waiting for my Ph.D. acceptance here in Chongqing, China as well. I am focusing on clinical works mainly, but also intend to do some basic research in the field of Urology. I also like to work on some article writing.

5. Md. Mahfujul Haque Haidary

Author Information: I want to contribute in the field of research and development with my previous earned knowledge and present learning to spread my skill and knowledge globally in the international areas and in my birth place Bangladesh to develop a sustaining growth for the country's economic development.

6. Muhammad Sharjeel Khalid

Author Information: I like to work for Expertizing in my field of Medicine & anything associated with it. Technology is revolutionizing this era & we should embed its usage in our field of medicine & surgery to yield good results in advancement & research.

7. Dattatreya Mukherjee

Author Information: Dattatreya Mukherjee is a MBBS Student, Research Assistant and Undergraduate research scholar in Jinan University, P.R China. His research interest is Oncology, Hematooncology, Neurology and Public Health. From last 4.5 years, he is connected to research works where he have conducted two major projects as PI and worked in over 100 scholarly work. He has presented his work in ASCO, AACR and BACR like top conferences in the field of Oncology

8. Md. Munnaf Hossen

Author Information: I am doing research focusing the pathogenesis of autoimmune diseases (AD) related to T cell mechanism. Particularly, I am interested to T and B cell mechanisms and their role on autoimmune disease (AD) development. Currently, I am doing bioinformatics analysis to identify novel SNP related with AD.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

